

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BANGOURA****FIRST NAME: CHEICK ALIMOU****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA – 401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 2011 on MacBook Pro.

ESSENTIALS OF EFFECTIVE ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

This response paper intends to discuss the EUCLID ACA-401D course period one. The ACA-401D period one offered an explicit focus on the fundamentals of a dissertation project for a student at the initial stages of the journey. The EUCLID'S ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack: period one enabled thorough insight into the essence of proper academic writing, with clearly explained vital elements and aspects of essay writing as the basis for future work on the graduate project. The coursepack contains carefully selected study materials put together to produce a comprehensive learning manual that enables students to become competent essay writers. It gives an overview of the step-by-step work on academic writing with regards to different dimensions of the dissertation process. This includes researching relevant and credible sources and engaging them, planning an argument, as well as drafting an essay (EUCLID 2019, 1-4), to list only a few. The EUCLID CMS crib sheet appears to be a useful guide to comprehending the path of pursuing a doctoral degree in that it presents valuable hints for organizing academic writing to reach successful outcomes in the process. Finally, the coursework incorporated a video on the basic course tutorial and methods of instruction explained. In this way, the course materials are of immense value to a student for substantial awareness of the basics and essence of developing a reliable academic voice and tone while working on the dissertation project.

2) REACTION TO THE COURSE MATERIAL

a) First Point Explained

The careful reading of the coursepack: period one was educative in terms of accepting and understanding of the fact that academic writing proficiency requires in-depth knowledge about a variety of language domains along with multiple writing and critical-thinking-related skills to be developed. Primarily, the resource presented a six-component chapter on essay writing (ibid.). This well-structured explanation of the essay as a concept and experience enables me to realize the complex validity of the principal aim of an essay "to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence" (EUCLID 2019, 1). However, achieving this fundamental goal requires much more effort. Apart from formulating assignment-specific questions and planning the line of argument on the grounds of the evaluation of the collected literature on the topic (EUCLID 2019, 1–2), proper crediting of the ‘borrowed’ ideas should be considered either through direct quotes or paraphrasing, namely, formatting of the paper (EUCLID 2019, 5–6). At the same time, the awareness of numerous grammar rules and issues regarding both British and American English is crucial. They are ranging from distinct spelling rules (EUCLID 2019, 27–28) and diverse terms and expressions (EUCLID 2019, 30) to specific equality vocabulary (EUCLID 2019, 32) among other issues. Overall, the source provides a large-scale quick reference guide to create an original and smoothly organized piece supported by expert opinions and an established respectable scholarly tone.

b) Second Point Explained

Likewise, in the basic ACA-401D tutorial video EUCLID presents its essential writing requirements, such as the use of its templates, file naming format, sub-headings, paragraph styles, and so on. The course materials offer a wide-scope guide for developing students’ writing capacity, with particular value derived in terms of a sophisticated approach towards source utilization and writing a quality academic work. For instance, the use of Zotero enables students to quickly insert sources with accurate citing of the sources; and draw their assumptions in the process. Moreover, studying the materials was invaluable for further understanding of planning an argument. Specifically, it was useful to interpret the concept explicitly. With the understanding and integrating the knowledge gained from the ACA–401D coursepack: period one, planning of an argument regarding literature-based notes could be imagined as a rather manageable activity, though requiring continuous learning and improving critical thinking, analytic, and writing skills. In this regard, the information on drafting an essay is crucial to recognizing the importance of this concept as a preliminary formulation of ideas related to the argument (EUCLID 2019, 2–3). The course materials and Turabian style provide guidance on avoiding plagiarism and poor paraphrasing through the proper use of citations and quotations. Placing longer quotations in a separate paragraph highlights critical points (EUCLID 2019, 5–13). Hence, this resource is essential for framing the

understanding of how to construct the academic paper to align with generally accepted standards of undergraduate writing.

c) Third Point Explained

Since the course and preparation of the dissertation project imply complex tasks or even a challenge, learning to organize and structure both time and activities is a vital skill to be developed. In this respect, the EUCLID (2019) ACA-401D period one coursework is fundamental to obtaining a holistic account on the nature of dissertation endeavor as “extended time working as a researcher,” having an opportunity of “on-the-job training,” and preparing a unique and scholarly work based on an individual research as an outcome of the dissertation journey. The course material is insightful and helpful in recognizing the anticipated misconceptions to be encountered in this context; identifying the main aspects and ways to mitigate them, and to be ready at each stage of the process, starting from proposing the research topic to the final defense of it. Similarly, period one course videos are useful for understanding the teaching strategies in the course scope to incorporate this methodology in the effective planning of the learning process. With these resources, considering the organization of productive learning is ensured.

3) CONCLUSION

The textual and audiovisual materials of the ACA-401D course period one have provided me with a valuable basis for comprehensive knowledge on wide-scope expectations set for the student pursuing a doctorate and completing a dissertation project. While the coursepack for period one offers a thorough overview of academic writing, the basic ACA-401 tutorial video expanded my understanding of scholarly requirements, focusing on the choice of style and formatting, as well as the correct use templates and referencing. Finally, the coursework is vital for me to manage the abundance of the multidimensional information and adequately allocate my time and resources to be well organized and to achieve the dissertation-based objectives at the different stages of the project. As a student in the Doctorate in Sustainable Development and Diplomacy program, I am convinced that using these tools will help me “sail to safer waters.”

4) REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.